

Title: Viscosity Prediction in a Physiologically Controlled Ventricular Assist Device

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INTRODUCTION:

Ventricular assist devices (VADs) are currently considered a valid alternative for end stage heart failure treatment when heart transplantation is not possible, despite the adverse events affecting the patient's quality of life. This is assumed to be due to the constant operation speed, leading to non-physiological hemodynamics. To counter this, the investigation of physiological control has been proposed, but the lack of long-term, implantable sensors still hampers their clinical implementation. Furthermore, the lack of reliable telemetric systems for continuous monitoring of the patients after discharge from a healthcare facility hinders the prediction or immediate detection of adverse events, which would allow their treatment at an early stage. To counteract this deficiency, non-invasive monitoring algorithms for various hemodynamic information have been proposed, leading to a dramatic improvement of the patient outcomes. Furthermore, continuous monitoring of patients hematocrit (HCT), would derive information regarding their health status and the interaction of the VAD with the circulation, as well as the enhancement of the estimated pump flow required, which is used for multiple purposes from the clinicians, such as for adjusting the pump speed during hospitalization. Therefore, reliable HCT is an important step towards better supervision of VAD-patients.

AIM:

A novel machine learning model is presented, which accurately predicts the blood-analog viscosity during support of a pathological circulation with a rotary ventricular assist device. The aim is the continuous prediction of the hematocrit of VAD patients with the benefit of a more reliable pump flow estimation and a possible early detection of adverse events, such as bleeding or pump thrombosis.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

A large dataset was generated with a blood pump connected to a hybrid mock circulation, by varying the pump speed, the physiological requirements of the modelled circulation and the viscosity of the blood-analog. The pump inlet pressure and the pump intrinsic signals were considered as inputs for the model. Gaussian process yielded models with the best performance, which were then combined using a variant of stacked generalization to derive the final model. The final model was evaluated with unseen testing data from the created data set.

RESULTS:

For these data, the model yielded a mean absolute deviation of 1.81% from the true HCT, while it proved to correctly predict the direction of the HCT change. It showed to be independent of the set speed and the condition of the simulated cardiovascular circulation.

CONCLUSIONS:

The accuracy of the prediction model allows to improve the quality of flow estimators and detect adverse events at an early stage. Its clinical application could provide the clinicians with reliable and important hemodynamic information of the patient, and, thus, enhance patient monitoring and supervision.

KEYWORDS:

Hematocrit prediction; Gaussian process; Ensembling; Rotary blood pump

BIOGRAPHY:

Menelaos Kanakis is currently pursuing a MSc in Robotics, Systems and Control at ETH Zurich in Switzerland, specializing in Machine Learning. In conjunction to his studies, he is also working as a research assistant in the Product Development Group in ETH Zurich, focusing on the use of Machine Learning to enhance the control systems that enable the physiological adaptation of ventricular assist devices, as well as online monitoring of the patients' health status for safer implantable VADs.